

IMPROVEMENT OF ACCOUNTING IN RAILWAY ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: In the article, some issues of the development of fixed assets accounting, the organization of fixed assets in railway transport enterprises are developed on the basis of changes in production and formulated proposals.

Keywords: assets, long-term assets, current assets, fixed assets.

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СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА НА ЖЕЛЕЗНОДОРОЖНЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ

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Abstract: В данной статье на основе изменений в производстве и предложений разработаны некоторые вопросы развития учёта основных фондов, организации основных фондов на предприятиях железнодорожного транспорта.

Keywords: активы, долгосрочные активы, оборотные средства, основные средства.

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ТЕМИР ЙЎЛ КОРХОНАЛАРИДА БУХГАЛТЕРИЯ ХИСОБИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ

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Abstract: Мазкур мақолада асосий воситалар ҳисобини юришти масалалари ёритилган бўлиб, темир йўл транспорти корхоналарида асосий воситалар ҳисобини ташкил этишнинг айрим масалалари буйича олиб борилган ўрганишлар асосида хулоса ва таклифлар шакллантирилган

Keywords: активлар, узок муддатли активлар, жорий активлар, асосий воситалар.

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Enter. Since rail transport enterprises provide services related to direct transportation, the provision of passenger or freight services, the recognition of income from the provision of services, is also important. The sale of tickets related to the transportation of passengers does not mean that income is generated.

The reason is that the services must be provided clearly, realistically. Only then will Income be recognized. However, even in this process, the provision of services is common, that is, there are cases when it is carried out from several people to several hundred persons at the same time, such as the return of tickets,

the cost of services and the income from them in advance or on the same day the service was carried out, there is no possibility to determine. Therefore, the issue of recognition of income at railway transport enterprises is also carried out in different order, depending on the nature of the network. In particular, the recognition of income when transporting goods by rail transport can be recognized by the delivery of cargo to the last destination, delivery to the border, delivery to the alamashinuv point.

At the same time, the recognition of income is associated not only with transportation by rail, but can also be delivered by the exchange of goods to road transport from the place where the rail transport line ends to the last destination. It can be seen from this that the recognition of income there is a need to organize a comprehensive account of receipts associated with the operation of freight transport. In this case, when developing a mechanism for recognizing income, it is necessary to establish recognition criteria for particular types of services.

Relevance of the research topic. In our research work, we found it necessary to consider controversial or problematic issues regarding the accounting of various objects of accounting. This is due to the fact that most scientific research work on rail transport covers the costs and issues related to their accounting. Continuing our studies, we will consider the issue of long-term assets at railway transport enterprises, including capital investments.

The imposition of a scientific problem. As you know, the role and importance of long-term assets in different industries and industries will differ. Because, depending on the direction of activity and the procedure for working with long-term assets, depending on the degree of their use, it is also required to attach special importance to accounting.

The correct choice of one method or another, which is being applied to only one main tool, leads to a significant impact on the cost of products, work and services of the same direction or industry, as well as taking measures to update the main tools, minimize the impact on the cost. In this regard, our country and foreign scientists have expressed different attitudes from their scientific research and development. The accounting of fixed assets has been studied in different directions in various research works and feedback has been expressed.

Including Researcher K. Based on the need to develop a universally accepted methodology for assessing the value of machinery and equipment due to the presence of specificity of the assessment of machinery and equipment by khomitov [4].

Z.Mamatov and C.Salahiddinovs recommend constant Organization of continuous re-evaluation of the main tools of the Enterprise, Re-evaluation is

carried out according to the main tools recognized as all assets, re-evaluation of the main tool objects according to the actual value on the day of Re-evaluation [5].

Researcher J.Nasriddinov cites that physical wear and tear can be classified into types that can and cannot be eliminated [6]. C.Abdullaev cited his views on the development of separate approaches to promoting the use of accelerated depreciation [7].

D.Gazibekov notes that " the accelerated depreciation method introduced in the practice of Uzbekistan allows you to reduce the service life of the main capital, but this practically excludes accelerated depreciation, narrows the measures to stimulate investment aimed at production " [8].

Ya.Noting that it is advisable to use the method of depreciation accelerated by Mustafakulov to fixed capital, thereby increasing the flow of investments, and especially to focus even more of the investments involved in agriculture on fixed capital, this process recognizes that it is optimal ways to achieve economic stability while giving its positive result [9].

C.Conclusions were made by Tashnazarov on what methods are used in international standards [10].

A.Tulyaganov proposes to define hanging forms of depreciation calculation on the main tools, citing the fact that the application of specific methods of calculating wear to the main tools leads to their effective use [11].

Research objective. It consists in the development of proposals and recommendations aimed at improving their accounting at railway transport enterprises on the basis of a scientific study on the accounting of fixed assets. Scientific essence. As we know, a capital inflows account is a process account associated with the purchase, creation of an object, usually fixed assets. Studies carried out by us on our facilities have shown that one of the main issues in maintaining the accounting of capital inflows is the modernization and reconstruction of the main instruments along with the current and capital repairs, the implementation of the current lease and the accounting of costs associated with these processes.

Therefore, first of all, we decided to study the demand for the main tools, as well as the essence of these three associated with it, namely, the concepts of overhaul, modernization, reconstruction, from the point of view of accounting. Because, the correct and complete interpretation of concepts in any regulatory and legal and methodological documents related to accounting ensures the correct and accurate accounting of accounting objects.

Research techniques. In the process of research, the theoretical and legal foundations of efficiency indicators were studied, many theoretical sources related

to the topic, logical thinking, scientific observation, methods of a systematic approach were used, relying on empirical research.

Analysis and key results. According to the national standard of accounting No. 5, the main tools are material assets that are held by the enterprise for use in the process of producing products, carrying out work or providing services for the long term, or for the purpose of carrying out administrative and social tasks [1].

Paying attention to this definition, it is stated that the main tools are assets. That is, the fact that it must be recognized as an asset to be the main tool is evident from the definition given to the main tools in the standard. However, in the national standard of accounting No. 5, there is a next issue that, if it is also related to the recognition of the main tools as assets. According to it, fixed assets are recognized as assets if: (a) there is confidence in the enterprise that in the future the economic benefit associated with the asset will come; (B) the value of the asset can be accurately assessed. This requirement is also for some time controversial, and in the case of the fulfillment of one of the two requirements, the standard does not provide a clear norm. Suppose the value of an asset can be assessed, however, this asset is not intended to bring economic benefit in relation to the asset in the future. The question arises, is it not recognized as the main tool? If we also consider the requirement for basic tools in our national standard, we will also have to consider some reasonable cases.

According to the national standard of current accounting, the composition of fixed assets includes material assets that simultaneously meet the following criteria:
A) if the service life is more than one year;

B) if the value of the items is more than fifty times the amount of the minimum monthly salary set in the Republic of Uzbekistan (at the time of purchase) for one unit (If we see the requirements themselves, then we can see that in itself lies the essence, which does not reveal the economic content of the concept of basic tools.

That is, it can serve for more than a year, but, the imposition of a requirement to be more than 50 times the amount of base calculation does not have any basis. Because, if in our current standard the fact that the head of the enterprise in the reporting year has the right to set the minimum limit on their value in order to take into account the items in the composition of fixed assets eliminates this requirement, then, on the second hand, according to tax law, the main tools listed in the national standard of accounting. But, as mentioned above, the fact that there is a requirement to meet two criteria at the same time, and the fact that the standard cites in the paragraph after this requirement that another sum can be set by the leader indicates that the requirement to accept the main tool as an asset is controversial.

The first requirement was that fixed assets be served and valued for more than a year, recognizing that tangible assets that meet that requirement are fixed assets. In this case, there are requirements for recognition as an asset again. If it is clear that the material is an asset, will it not be recognized as an asset? The first requirement provides requirements for the inclusion of tangible assets in the composition of fixed assets. That is, it is provided that the asset already recognized as an asset is included in the main tool. Again, in paragraph 6, it is a matter of debate whether the value transferred to the principal means by being recognized as the same material asset is recognized as the asset again.

In our opinion, the citation of recognition as an asset in the future of economic benefit in the second requirement does not make sense. Because the material asset implies economic benefit, since the purpose of maintaining such assets is also economic enjoyment. If there are basic tools that serve in a direction that does not bring economic benefit, will they not be credited as the main tool (for example, the allocation of one bus for charitable purposes, etc.). The second requirement is that while the asset value can be assessed, the underlying tools are recognized as assets.

This requirement also does not correspond with the content when we learn in close connection with the previous requirement. If one of the mandatory requirements for the main tool is related to its value, and the requirement to serve for more than a year is also met and recognized as the main tool, how correct is it to impose a value requirement on it. The reason is, the requirement to recognize as an asset if the main tool, which meets a requirement of no less than 50 times the amount of base calculation to be the main tool, or meets the norm established by the leader, again evaluates its value, shows how confusing these requirements are, eliminating their meaning and essence (Table 1).

In the international standards of financial reporting, including the international standard of accounting No. 16, it is recognized that fixed assets are material assets that are intended for the production or supply of products, or the provision of services, or leasing to other parties, or for administrative purposes, and that are expected to be used for a period longer than [2].

As can be seen from this norm, the main tools are not defined precisely according to the value or the focus on taking a person. It is taken into account that its use in the first place, and in the second, the service period is more than a specified period (one year). Therefore, in our opinion, when a demand is placed on the main tools, it is necessary to first demand that they be recognized as assets, and then recognized as the main tool.

In our opinion, in order to ensure the requirements of national accounting standards and International Financial Reporting Standards, as well as logical, inextricable connection, it is advisable to include material assets in the main

instruments that meet the following requirements: – to serve for more than a year; – to be used in the production, service process. It should be understood that production, when it is said that it participates in the service process, also directly participates in administrative purposes. The value, or whether it can be evaluated, must be cited in the requirements Prior to the recognition of the underlying tool as the underlying tool. Together with the requirement placed on the main tools, we consider the conditions for changing its value, changes in the amount of depreciation, and changes in the term of Service.

The national standards of accounting provide the conditions for the change in the value of the main tool, in which, under complex conditions, it is possible to increase its value, that is, its initial value. That is, at the request of the standard, the issue of increasing its value on the basis of the useful service life of the main tool is partially covered. According to it, the useful service life is the amount of product (works and services) that the enterprise uses the asset gan time period or the enterprise is intended to obtain from the use of this asset. Additional construction, provision of additional equipment, reconstruction, modernization and technical rearmament are useful service periods for the main tools entered into use upon completion of the work, the period of time in which the main tools are used by the enterprise from the moment these works are completed, or the amount of products (works, services) that the enterprise expects to receive from the use of these.

Paying attention to this requirement, the conclusion follows that the useful service life of the main tool can change at the expense of its modernization, reconstruction, technical armament. However, the question of whether modernization, reconstruction will increase the initial value of the main tool is not only clearly not given in the current regulatory documents, but the conditions for adding them to the initial value are complex and almost impossible. That is, the initial cost of the main tool was prepared by the author on the basis of the requirements of the khara1 BHMS made on the creation (construction and completion) or purchase of the main tools. there is a norm of formation on the basis of the cost of Jats, including taxes paid and non-reimbursable (fees), as well as delivery and assembly, installation, commissioning and any other costs that are directly related to bringing the asset into working condition for its intended use [1].

From the requirement of this norm, it follows that the initial value of the main tool is also added to the costs associated with bringing it into working condition. However, in another requirement of the national standard of accounting No. 5, it is established that these basic tools are allowed to change the initial value of the main tools adopted for accounting in the case of additional construction, provision of additional equipment, reconstruction, modernization, technical rearmament, partial completion and their reevaluation [1].

As can be seen from the standard requirement, the initial value of the main tools can change, along with a number of other costs, at the expense of modernization and reconstruction. However, the requirements of Paragraph 22 of the standard practically eliminate all the above issues. Because at the request of this item, all other expenses that do not increase their initial value and increase their future economic benefit in the event of an increase in the future economic benefit from the use of capital flows into the main means should be recognized as expenses during the period in which they were carried out.

It should be noted that the imposition of a requirement in this requirement that in the future it will increase economic profit limits the possibility of adding the costs for the modernization of the main tool to an increase in its initial value. Because, in very few cases, the modernization of the main tool serves to increase the economic benefit that it receives from it, or there is no possibility to determine whether such a benefit has increased. Therefore, in most cases, it is assessed as a problematic issue to improve the main tool, to take the costs incurred in the overhaul to their initial value, or to take into account them as a period cost. In paragraph 23, however, the costs of additional construction of fixed assets, provision of additional equipment, reconstruction, modernization, technical rearmament, after their termination, if as a result of them, the normative indicators of the use of fixed assets were initially adopted (useful service life, capacity, quality of application, etc.).k.) is defined to increase the initial value of such an object if it improves (increases) [1].

This requirement will further entangle all the cases considered by us. Because, the requirement that the normative indicators initially adopted in the demand be increased is much more controversial. For example, even if the entire seats of a passenger-carrying bus are replaced by its initial accepted normative indicator, the capacity of Passenger Reception does not increase. On the contrary, comfort can be reduced at the expense of providing and the legal basis for adding the costs made to this to its initial value does not give way.

However, there will be a need to bring additional elegance in a competitive environment, not an increase in the previous production capacity, but the convenience of users of the service, to adapt them to their taste, in a word, to the Times. According to the national standard of accounting No. 5, work on modernization is included due to changes in the technological or service purpose of the main tools, increased loading and further improvement in quality. From this norm it can be seen that the sentence of modernization was not used in the sense of modernization for the purpose of accounting. Here we are talking about a change in purpose, loading and improving quality. Reconstruction works include the reconstruction of existing fixed assets, which are associated with improving

production and increasing its technical and economic indicators for the purpose of increasing production capacity, improving the quality of products (works, services) and changing the nomenclature, as well as carried out on the reconstruction project of fixed assets.

From the above, it can be seen that the issue of reconstruction of fixed assets should also be aimed at increasing production capacities, improving economic indicators. Therefore, it is desirable that these concepts are theoretically and methodically perfect for a clear and correct Organization of accounting in railway transport enterprises, in which every change in the value of the main tool should be justified. In a study on this subject, Z.A general approach to the issue of modernization was taken by Mukhammadiev, who also introduces reconstruction into the modernization of enterprises. At the same time, the author focuses on investments in modernization [3]. However, the question of when to recognize the expenditure also made in this research work as the cost of modernization has not been disclosed. The author does not emphasize studies on the issue of recognition of modernization costs, considering it as investment, capital investments, offers and recommendations for further improvement of the scheme of capital investments 0800. A proposal has been put forward to change the name of schyot 0800 to "accounts accounting for modernization processes". However, the fact that even spending on all the main tool or other long-term assets will not be modernization has been ignored by the author.

As can be seen from the above, in order to recognize the costs associated with the overhaul, modernization, reconstruction of fixed assets, current repairs as a cost, it is advisable to introduce a clear norm, norm on each of them. At the same time, this norm should be reflected in the legislation on accounting, including national standards and accounting policies.

Conclusions and suggestions. From the above, we can draw the following conclusions: when a requirement is placed on the main tools, it is necessary to first put the requirement that they be recognized as assets, then as the main tool. In this case, it is advisable to include material assets that meet the requirements of national accounting standards and International Financial Reporting Standards, as well as the requirement for more than a year of Service and production, use in the service process of the main instruments in order to ensure a logical, inextricable connection. From the point of view of accounting, the reconstruction of fixed assets is the complete or partial transformation of the fixed assets due to the need to produce the fixed assets, making technological changes due to the need to affect its shape. Reconstruction costs are determined in the accounting policy of the enterprise and increase its initial value.

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